

Analysis of the influence of sensory experience, satiety value, menu selection, hygiene, and price on customer satisfaction and customer loyalty at the upper-level fine dining customers in Medan

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Abstract:

Food businesses must adapt to changing times while continuing to meet the needs of their customers to maintain their trust and loyalty and to increase customer satisfaction through sensory experience, satiety value, menu selection, hygiene and price. The purpose of this study is to investigate the effects of sensory experience, satiety value, menu selection, hygiene and price towards customer satisfaction and customer *loyalty*. The data was gathered by administering a questionnaire to 125 people who had used the Upper-Level Fine Dining at least twice in the previous one year. SPSS 26.0 software was used to analyze the data. The empirical findings indicated that Sensory Experience has positive significant on customer satisfaction, Satiety Value e has positive significant on customer satisfaction, Menu Selection e hasn't on customer satisfaction, Hygiene has positive significant on customer satisfaction, Price has positive significant on customer satisfaction, Customer Satisfaction has positive significant on customer loyalty.

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Introduction

A fine-dining restaurant has a different impression than a restaurant in general, it has an impression that is luxurious enough to be enjoyed when eating the menu that has been served (Tiofani, 2021). To satisfy customers, food service is one of the other important factors that the service needs to be considered, the quality of food will depend on several other factors such as how to arrange the food on the plate, the color of the food served, aesthetics, and music is also one of the factors that affect human food intake (Mamalaki.E, et al, 2017). According to Condrasky (2007), professional chefs have the most important role in preparing and serving healthy food in fine dining restaurants. Pay a retain is often a much more effective strategy than efforts to attract new customers because customer loyalty is a customer commitment to a brand or store that is positive in the long term (Tjiptono, 2017). To develop sensory experience, satiety value, menu selection, hygiene, and price requires positive ratings (Chou & Hsu, 2016; Harris & Goode, 2010). This study also includes two more variables, loyalty and satisfaction. loyalty variable is added to deepen the understanding on how the company's ability to manage their customer feedback to alter customer perceptions on the Upper-Level Fine Dining at Medan and Loyalty is added to understand its relationship with sensory experience, satiety value, menu selection, hygiene, and price and how it will influence the user's buying behavior. The Upper-Level Fine Dining at Medan have several satisfaction indicators: I will spread the positive, i would recommend to friends, family and others, i would recommend to someone who asks for advice. *Sensory Experience* indicator consists of: seasoning the right food, the food served is delicious, visually appealing food, food served at the appropriate temperature, food served fresh, the food served is flavorful, food served less tasty. Satiety value indicator consists of: Portions of food that are already fi, food served at the right time, foods that have high nutritional value, foods that are easy to chew, *Menu Selection* indicator consists of: offers a variety of menu options, healthy menu, menu that can be consumed during the diet, offering unique of menu. Hygiene indicator consists of: not serving food neatly and properly, clean and hygienic place, cleaned periodically. Price indicator consists of: unaffordable price, offers affordable prices, offer food that is worth the price. Customer satisfaction indicator consists of: i am satisfied with the experience, i feel happy to have visited, i would recommend to someone.

Literature Review

Sensory Experience

Sensory experience is an attempt to create experiences related to the five senses, including sight, sound, smell, taste and touch (Tiwari, 2019). Lim et (2020) explained that sensory experience (SE) has significant effect on customer satisfaction. Thus, we tested the following hypothesis:

H1: sensory experience has influence on customer satisfaction

Satiety Value

Originality of design defined as Innovative idea that is developed by the person who created it and which derives from the source. The notion that is opposed to that of imitation products also refers to things that are extraordinary, uncommon, and unique (Satir, 2015). Lim et (2020) explained that satiety value (SV) has significant effect on customer satisfaction. Thus, we tested the following hypothesis:

H2: Satiety value has influence on customer satisfaction

Menu Selection

In research conducted by Ilham (2018), States if there is a significant influence between menu selection on customer satisfaction. Lim et (2020) explained that menu selection (M) has significant effect on customer satisfaction. Thus, we tested the following hypothesis:

H3: Menu selection has influence on customer satisfaction.

Hygiene

Lim et (2020) and Sembiring (2018) explained that hygiene (H) has significant effect on customer satisfaction. Thus, we tested the following hypothesis:

H4: Hygiene has influence on customer satisfaction

Price

Price is one of the factors that affect customer satisfaction because the price has been set by the company to be a benchmark to achieve satisfaction, this is because the price is one of the considerations for customers. Lim et (2020) and Yuliana (2018) explained that price (P) has significant effect on customer satisfaction. Thus, we tested the following hypothesis:

H5: Price has influence on customer satisfaction

Customer Satisfaction

customer loyalty refers to a customer's commitment to consistently repeat a preferred purchase or service despite situational and marketing efforts to change customer behavior (Sidabutar and Dharmayanti, 2017), Lim et (2020) and Tsabala (2018) explained that customer satisfaction (CS) has significant effect on customer loyalty. Thus, we tested the following hypothesis

H6: Customer Satisfaction has influence on Customer Loyalty

Research Issue and Methodology

This study is using quantitative approach with the population were taken from customers of the Upper-Level Fine Dining in Medan with the age of 18-60 years old. The sampling technique used in non-probability sampling using questionnaire as the main tool for collecting the responses. In this study, the researchers used purposive sampling technique, a sampling method used to select people who have extensive knowledge of the phenomenon studied. The number of respondents collected are 125 customers of the Upper-Level Fine Dining in Medan. The research model can be seen below:

Figure 3-1 Research Model

Source: Lim 2020

Findings and Discussion

In this study, the relationships between the variables were tested using the SSPSS. SPSS 26.0 is the statistical analysis tool used in this research to answer the question formulated before. After the questionnaires have been filled out and sent back, descriptive statistics-analysis must be done. In figure 4-1, it shows the majority of the respondent are Female with 78 Respondent (62.4%) and male respondent with 47 respondents (37.6%).

Figure 4-1 Respondent Characteristic by Gender

Source: Author

Figure 4-2 Respondent Characteristic by Age

Source: Author

Table 4-1 shows that most of the customer age of the Upper-Level Fine Dining as many as 55.2% or 69 respondents were respondents aged 18-35 years, 31.2% or 39 respondents were respondents aged 35-50 years and 13.6% or 17 respondents were respondents aged 50-60 years. The majority of customers at the Upper-Level Fine Dining are 18-35 years old.

Table 4.1: Respondent by Age

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	18-35	69	55.2	55.2	55.2
	35-50	39	31.2	31.2	86.4
	50-60	17	13.6	13.6	100.0
	Total	125	100.0	100.0	

Source: Author

Table 4-2 Descriptive Statistic

Variable	Indicator	Description	Descriptive Statistic	
			Mean	SD
Sensory Experience (X1)	SE 1	The condiments from the food The Upper Level Fine Dining taste appropriate	3.616	0.8539
	SE 2	The food served by the Upper Level Fine Dining has a good taste	3.736	0.9082
	SE 3	The food served at the Upper Level Fine Dining is visually appealing	3.712	0.8014
	SE 4	The Upper Level Fine Dining meals are served at appropriate temperatures	3.744	0.7819
	SE 5	Food served The Upper Level Fine Dining using fresh ingredients	3.712	0.8310
	SE 6	The food served by the Upper Level Fine Dining has a delicious aroma	3.776	0.8507
Satiety (X2)	SV 1	Portions of the Upper Level Fine Dining meals are just right	3.720	0.8289
	SV2	Meals from the Upper Level Fine Dining are served in a timely manner	3.800	0.9419
	SV3	Food from the Upper Level Fine Dining has a high nutritional value	3.768	0.8811
	SV 4	The food from the Upper Level Fine Dining is easy to chew	3.800	0.8890
Menu Selectio (X3)	MS 1	The Upper Level Fine Dining offers a wide selection of attractive signature menus	3.728	0.8649
	MS 2	The Upper Level Fine Dining has a variety of varied signature menus	3.680	0.8092
	MS 3	The Upper Level Fine Dining offers a variety of menus that can generally be consumed by various groups	3.752	0.7032
Hygiene (X4)	H 1	The Upper Level Fine Dining uses food with hygiene-assured processing	3.616	0.8687
	H 2	The Upper Level Fine Dining provides a dine in area that is kept clean	3.864	0.8265
	H 3	The Upper Level Fine Dining uses tableware that is guaranteed hygiene	3.792	0.7961
Price (X5)	P 1	The Upper Level Fine Dining offers appropriate prices for food and beverages on offer	3.632	0.8086
	P 2	The Upper Level Fine Dining offers affordable prices	3.752	0.8039
	P 3	The Upper Level Fine Dining offers food and beverages at prices that match the size of the food and beverages on offer	3.712	0.7227
Customer Satisfaction (Y1)	CS 1	I was satisfied with the dining experience at the upstairs Fine Dining.	3.768	0.8046
	CS 2	I was satisfied with the wide variety of food and drinks at the top level Fine Dining.	3.824	0.8039
	CS 3	I was satisfied with the comfort of a place to eat on the top level of Fine Dining	3.816	0.7227
Loyalty (Y2)	CL 1	I will continue to revisit The Upper Level Fine Dining in the future	3.824	0.8334
	CL 2	I would recommend The Upper Level Fine Dining my friends	3.856	0.8299
	CL 3	I would make The Upper Level Fine Dining my first choice for dine in compared to other similar restaurants	3.744	0.7819

Source: Author

Based on the results on the table 4-2 above, all of the indicators standard deviation is below 2.0 which shows that the responses given by the respondent are homogeneous. The indicator SE.6 or The food served by the Upper Level Fine Dining has a delicious aroma in sensory experience variable has the highest standard deviation value with 0.8507 this indicates that the respondent gives answer to sensory experience least homogeneous compared with other variables.

Validity and Reliability Test

Validity test of r count must greater than r table to be perceived as valid in forming constructs and can be used to build models.

Table 4-3 Validity Test

Variable	Indicator	Description	Validity Test	
			r count	r table
Sensory Experience (X1)	SE 1	The condiments from the food The Upper Level Fine Dining taste appropriate	0.728	0.176
	SE 2	The food served by the Upper Level Fine Dining has a good taste	0.781	0.176
	SE 3	The food served at the Upper Level Fine Dining is visually appealing	0.616	0.176
	SE 4	The Upper Level Fine Dining meals are served at appropriate temperatures	0.771	0.176
	SE 5	Food served The Upper Level Fine Dining using fresh ingredients	0.719	0.176
	SE 6	The food served by the Upper Level Fine Dining has a delicious aroma	0.767	0.176
Satiety Value (X2)	SV 1	Portions of the Upper Level Fine Dining meals are just right	0.704	0.176
	SV2	Meals from the Upper Level Fine Dining are served in a timely manner	0.709	0.176
	SV3	Food from the Upper Level Fine Dining has a high nutritional value	0.821	0.176
	SV 4	The food from the Upper Level Fine Dining is easy to chew	0.861	0.179
Menu Selection (X3)	MS 1	The Upper Level Fine Dining offers a wide selection of attractive signature menus	0.554	0.176
	MS 2	The Upper Level Fine Dining has a variety of varied signature menus	0.661	0.176
	MS 3	The Upper Level Fine Dining offers a variety of menus that can generally be consumed by various groups	0.660	0.176
Hygiene (X4)	H 1	The Upper Level Fine Dining uses food with hygiene-assured processing	0.650	0.176
	H 2	The Upper Level Fine Dining provides a dine in area that is kept clean	0.685	0.176
	H 3	The Upper Level Fine Dining uses tableware that is guaranteed hygiene	0.563	0.176
Price (X5)	P 1	The Upper Level Fine Dining offers appropriate prices for food and beverages on offer	0.750	0.176
	P 2	The Upper Level Fine Dining offers affordable prices	0.708	0.176
	P 3	The Upper Level Fine Dining offers food and beverages at prices that match the size of the food and beverages on offer	0.686	0.176
Customer Satisfaction (Y1)	CS 1	I was satisfied with the dining experience at the upstairs Fine Dining.	0.777	0.176
	CS 2	I was satisfied with the wide variety of food and drinks at the top level Fine Dining.	0.625	0.176
	CS 3	I was satisfied with the comfort of a place to eat on the top level of Fine Dining	0.662	0.176
Loyalty (Y2)	CL 1	I will continue to revisit The Upper Level Fine Dining in the future	0.777	0.176
	CL 2	I would recommend The Upper Level Fine Dining my friends	0.886	0.176
	CL 3	I would make The Upper Level Fine Dining my first choice for dine in compared to other similar restaurants	0.723	0.176

Source: Author

Reliability Test

Table 4-4 Reliability Test

Variable	Reliability Test	
	Cronbach's Alpha	Based on Standardized Item Critical Number
Customer Loyalty	0.903	0.60
Customer Satisfaction	0.828	0.60
Price	0.847	0.60
Hygiene	0.790	0.60
Menu Selection	0.788	0.60
Satiety Value	0.898	0.60
Sensory Experience	0.901	0.60

Source: Author

Each construct has a construct reliability value of more than 0.60. This means that these indicators are reliable in expressing the constructs of sensory experience (SE), satiety value (SV), menu selection (MS), hygiene (H), price (P), and customer satisfaction (CS), and loyalty (CL).

Normality Test

Table 4-5 Kolmogorov Smirnov (K-S) Test

Equation	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	Critical Number	Description
SE, SV, MS, H, P → CS	0.200c, d	>0.05	Normally Distributed
SE, SV, MS, H, P → CL	0.05 ^c	>0.05	Normally Distributed

Source: Author

From the output below can be seen in the column Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z can be seen that the significance of all variables greater than 0.05 it can be concluded that the sample data variable sensory experience, satiety value, menu selection, hygiene, price, customer satisfaction and customer loyalty are normally distributed.

Figure 4-4 Scatterplot of Normality Test

Source: Author

Multicollinearity Test

Table 4-4 Multicollinearity Test

Variable	Tolerance	VIF	Result
SE *CS	0.441	2.268	Multicollinearity-Free
SV*CS	0.383	2.612	Multicollinearity-Free
MS*CS	0.268	3.736	Multicollinearity-Free
H*CS	0.258	3.874	Multicollinearity-Free
P*CS	0.271	3.683	Multicollinearity-Free
CS*CL	1.000	1.000	Multicollinearity-Free

Source: Author

From the output below can be seen in the column VIF and tolerance values from sensory experience (SE), satisfaction value (SV), menu selection (MS), hygiene (H), price (P), and customer satisfaction (CS) (VIF<10), (Tolerance>0.1), this means that there is no multicollinearity between independent variables in the regression model.

Heteroscedasticity Test

Table 4-6 Heteroscedasticity Test

Variable	Unstandardized Residual Sig. (2-tailed)	Critical Number	Result
SE*CS	0.525	0.05	Homogen
SV*CS	0.847	0.05	Homogen
MS*CS	0.945	0.05	Homogen
H*CS	0.752	0.05	Homogen
P*CS	0.517	0.05	Homogen
CS*CL	0.059	0.05	Homogen

Source: Author

Each construct has a construct heteroscedasticity value of more than 0.05. This means that these indicators are homogen in expressing the sensory experience (SE), satiety value (SV), menu selection (MS), hygiene(H), price (H) terhadap customer satisfaction (CS).

Figure 4-5 Scatterplot of Heteroscedasticity Test

Source: Author

Linearity Test

Table 4-7 Linearity Test

Variable	Linearity	Standard	Result
SE*CS	0.000	0.05	Linier
SV*CS	0.000	0.05	Linier
MS*CS	0.000	0.05	Linier
H*CS	0.000	0.05	Linier
P*CS	0.000	0.05	Linier
CS*CL	0.000	0.05	Linier

Source: Author

All output variables in the table above have a significance value of linearity below 0.05. It can be concluded between variables customer satisfaction with sensory experience there is a significant linear relationship, customer satisfaction with satisfaction value there is a significant linear relationship, customer satisfaction with menu selection there is a significant linear relationship, customer satisfaction with hygiene there is a significant linear relationship, customer satisfaction with price there is a significant linear relationship, and customer loyalty with customer satisfaction.

Multiple Regression Analysis

Table 4-8 Multiple Regression Analysis (SE, SV, MS, H, P*CS)

Variable	Standardized Coefficients
Sensory experience	0.226
Satiety Value	0.223
Menu Selection	0.114
Hygiene	0.254
Price	0.221

Source: Author

$$CS = b_1 .SE + b_2 .SV + b_3 .MS + b_4 .H + b_5 .P$$

$$CS = 0.226.SE + 0.223.SV + 0.114.MS + 0.254.H + 0.221$$

$$CL = b_6 .CS$$

$$CL = 0.845.CS$$

From the above explanation that the coefficient marked positive indicates a change in the direction of the independent variable to the dependent variable. As for the coefficient marked negative shows the change that is not in the direction of the independent variable to the dependent variable. In the regression calculation above, shows all independent variables have coefficients marked positive. The coefficient marked positive shows the change in the direction between the independent variable to the dependent variable. In the regression calculation above, shows all independent variables have coefficients marked positive.

Coefficient of Determination

Table 4-9 Coefficient Of Determination

Variable	Coefficient Of Determination
SE, SV, MS, H, P*CS	0.827
CS*CL	0.714

Source: Author

Based on the output obtained R2 of 0,827 or 82.7%. This shows that the percentage of contribution of sensory experience, satiety value, menu selection, hygiene, and price to the dependent variable of customer satisfaction is 82.7%. This means that the independent variable is able to explain 82.7% of the dependent variable, while the remaining 17.3% is influenced by other variables that are not included in this research model. Based on The value for R2 of 0714 or 71.4%. This shows that the percentage contribution of customer satisfaction effect on the dependent variable of customer loyalty is 71.4%. This means that the independent variable is able to explain 71.4% of dependent variables, while the remaining 28.6% is influenced by other variables that are not included in this research model.

Hypothesis Test

Table 4-10 Coefficient Of Determination

Hip	Influence Between Variables	Sig.	Standard	Result
H1	CS*SE	0.000	0.05	Accepted
H2	CS*SV	0.000	0.05	Accepted
H3	CS*MS	0.118	0.05	Rejected
H4	CS*H	0.001	0.05	Accepted
H5	CS*P	0.003	0.05	Accepted
H6	CL*CS	0.000	0.05	Accepted

Source: Author

Table 4-10 shows that the C.R. value for *Sensory Experience* (H1), *Satiety Value* (H2), *Hygiene* (H4), *Price* (H5), *Customer Satisfaction* (H6), significant values that are less than 0.05. This means that the relationships between the studied variables are significant. *Menu Selection* on customer satisfaction (H3) significant values that are grater than 0.05. This means that H3 an did not show a significant effect between the variables.

Discussion

According to the findings of this study, sensory experience, satiety value, hygiene, price all have a positive and significant influence on customer satisfaction and also positively influenced by customer loyalty. menu selection has no significant influence on customer satisfaction. Table 4-11 shows that IN-3 is the most accurate predictors in hygiene variable with validity value of 0.781.

Table 4-11 Hygiene (H) indicators

Variable	Indicator	Validity Value	Mean
<i>Hygiene (X4)</i>	H 1	0.650	3.616
	H 2	0.685	3.864
	H 3	0.563	3.792

Source: Author

The second most influential variable on customer satisfaction is hygiene with regression coefficient of 0.254 and P-value of 0.001. The result shows the similarity with Lim (2020) study where hygiene influence customer satisfaction. Table 4-11 shows that H.2 is the most accurate predictor of hygiene variable with validity value of 0.685.

Table 4-8 Sensory Experience (SE) indicators

Variable	Indicator	Validity Value	Mean
<i>Sensory Experience (X1)</i>	SE 1	0.728	3.616
	SE 2	0.781	3.736
	SE 3	0.616	3.712
	SE 4	0.771	3.744
	SE 5	0.719	3.712
	SE 6	0.767	3.776

Source: Author

The third most influential variable on customer satisfaction is sensory experience with regression coefficient of 0.226 and P-value of 0.001. The result shows the similarity with Lim (2020) study where sensory experience influence customer satisfaction. Table 4-9 shows that SE.2 is the most accurate predictor of sensory experience variable with validity value of 0.781.

Table 4-12 Satiety Value (SVR) indicators

Variable	Indicator	Validity Value	Mean
<i>Satiety Value (X2)</i>	SV 1	0.704	3.720
	SV 2	0.709	3.800
	SV 3	0.821	3.768
	SV 4	0.861	3.800

Source: Author

The fourth most influential variable on customer satisfaction is satiety value with regression coefficient of 0.223 and P-value of 0.000. The result shows the similarity with Lim (2020) study where satiety value influence customer satisfaction. Table 4-12 shows that SV.3 is the most accurate predictor of satiety value variable with validity value of 0.861.

Table 4-13 Price (P) indicators

Variable	Indicator	Lambda Loading	Mean
<i>Price (X5)</i>	P 1	0.750	3.632
	P 2	0.708	3.752
	P 3	0.686	3.712

Source: Author

The fifth most influential variable on customer satisfaction is price with regression coefficient of 0.221 and P-value of 0.003. The result shows the similarity with Lim (2020) study where

price influence customer satisfaction. Table 4-13 shows that P.1 is the most accurate predictor of price variable with validity value of 0.750

Conclusion

This study's model was created to understand the influence between the sensory experience, satiety value, menu selection, hygiene, price and the influence of customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. From the study conducted, sensory experience, satiety value, hygiene, price all have a positive and significant influence on customer satisfaction. Therefore, the managerial implication will revolve around the significant variables. First, for sensory experience variable, it is suggested to attention to this in order to create an excellent level of satisfaction that has an impact on the level of consumer loyalty increases. As well as serving food in a hot state in terms of food such as rice. This is in order to create a high level of consumption. With the presentation of hot food can encourage consumer enjoyment. Second, for Satiety value variable, it is suggested that The Upper-Level Fine Dining improve innovation and creativity that better create an increase in consumer visits to this restaurant. It is necessary to make improvements with menus such as attractive appearance and supported with luxurious equipment and supplies. Typical menu choices can also be done creativity by adding many options in order to meet the wishes of consumers. Third, for Menu selection, it is suggested that The Upper-Level Fine Dining creating distinctive menu variations so that consumers can remember the food. In addition, it is necessary to create drinks that match the characteristics of the Upper-Level Fine Dining and can be a mainstay so that every consumer visiting the restaurant wants to order these drinks and food. In addition, in order to compete with other restaurants. Fourth, for Hygiene, it is suggested that The Upper-Level Fine Dining need to add cleaning staff so that the environment can be maintained with clean and tidy then can add facilities and infrastructure better hygiene and a lot so that the cleaning staff can be helped. Fifth, for price, it is recommended for The Upper-Level Fine Dining need to add cleaning staff so that the environment can be maintained with a clean and tidy then can add facilities and infrastructure better hygiene and a lot so that the cleaning staff can be helped.

Suggestions for further study

This research examined the impact of the **sensory experience, satiety value, hygiene, price** on customer satisfaction and loyalty. This would allow the researcher to compare various findings regarding the widespread implementation of the sensory experience, satiety value, hygiene, price in the era of food and beverage sector. It is also suggested to add new variables to the research, such as service scape, food quality, location.

References

- Abdullah, T dan Francis T. (2020). *Manajemen Pemasaran*. Depok : PT Raja Grafindo Persada.
- Adam, M. (2018). *Manajemen Pemasaran Jasa Teori dan Aplikasi*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- Adriyanti, A.W. (2018). Gambaran Kesesuaian Siklus Menu, Besar Porsi, Tingkat Kecukupan Energi dan Protein Remaja di Panti Asuhan Baitul Falah Semarang. Repository: Diploma thesis, *Universitas Muhammadiyah Semarang*
- Capes. (2018). *Growth charts for the United States: methods and development*. Washington: Department of Health and Human Services.
- Cohen, J. (1988). *Statistical power analysis for the behavioral sciences*. Hillsdale, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates. (pp. 262, 263, 299).
- Ghozali, I, 2005. *Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate Dengan Program SPSS*. Edisi Ketiga, Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro, Semarang.
- Griffin, J, (2019), *Customer Loyalty, Menumbuhkan dan Mempertahankan. Kesetiaan Pelanggan*. Alih Bahasa Dwi Kartini Yahya. Jakarta: Erlangga.
- Hasan, A. (2018). *Marketing dan Kasus-Kasus Pilihan*. Jakarta: CAPS.
- Lim, W, M. 2022, Marketing luxury services beyond affluence in the new normal: Insights from fine dining during the coronavirus pandemic. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 66, (2022), 102936
- Malau, H. (2017). *Manajemen Pemasaran*. Alfabeta, Bandung.
- Manap, A. (2018). *Revolusi Manajemen Pemasaran*. Edisi Pertama, Mitra. Wacana Media, Jakarta
- Murdijati, G. 2017. *Pendidikan Konsumsi Pangan*. Jakarta Percetakan PT Fajar Interpretama Mandiri.

- Mustikawati, (2017). Perilaku Personal Hygiene Pada Pemulung di TPA Kedaung Wetan Tanggerang, Forum Ilmiah. *Jurnal Kesehatan Lingkungan*, 10, 1-27.
- Ningsih, R. (2019). Penyuluhan Hygiene Sanitasi Makanan dan Minuman, Serta Kualitas Makanan yg Dijajakan Pedagang di Lingkungan SDN Kota Samarinda, *Jurnal Kesehatan Masyarakat. Jurnal Kesehatan Masyarakat*, 10(1), 64-72.
- Oktaviani WD, Saraswati LD, Rahfiludin MZ. Hubungan Kebiasaan Konsumsi Fastfood, Aktivitas fisik, Pola Konsumsi, Karakteristik Remaja dan Orang Tua dengan Indeks Massa Tubuh (IMT) (Studi Kasus Pada Siswa SMA Negeri 9 Semarang Tahun 2019). *Jurnal Kesehatan Lingkungan*, 11, 45-51.
- Priansa, D. J. (2018). *Perilaku Konsumen dalam Persaingan Bisnis Kontemporer*. Bandung: ALFABETA.
- Rachman. (2017). *Manajemen Pemasaran*, Ombak : Yogyakarta
- Sandjaja dan Atmarita. (2019). *Kamus Gizi Pelengkap Kesehatan Keluarga*. Jakarta: PT Kompas Media Nusantara
- Sangadji, E.M., dan Sopiah. (2018). *Prilaku Konsumen: Pendekatan Praktis. Disertai:Himpunan Jurnal Penelitian*. Yogyakarta: Penerbit Andi.
- Sari, W.A.P. (2019). Pemberian Enzim Papain untuk Meningkatkan Pemanfaatan Protein Pakan dan Pertumbuhan Benih Ikan Nila Larasati (*Oreochromis niloticus* Var.). Skripsi. Program Studi Budidaya Perairan, *Jurnal Perikanan dan Ilmu Kelautan*.
- Silaen, Sofar. (2018). *Metodologi Penelitian Sosial untuk Penulisan Skripsi dan Tesis*. Bogor: In Media.
- Siregar, S. (2017). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif dilengkapi dengan perbandingan perhitungan manual & SPSS*. Jakarta: kencana. Prenada media
- Smith, A. (2017). *An Inquiry into the Nature and Causes of the Wealth of Nations*. London: Methuen & Co. LTD
- Sudaryono. (2016). *Manajemen Pemasaran Teori dan Implementasi*. Yogyakarta: C.V. Andi Offset.
- Sugiarto, E. (2017). *Menyusun Proposal Penelitian Kualitatif Skripsi dan Tesis*. Yogyakarta : Suaka Media.
- Sulistyoningsih, H. 2018. *Gizi Untuk Kesehatan Ibu Dan Anak*. Jakarta : Graha ilmu.
- Sujarweni, W. 2019. *Metode Penelitian*. Yogyakarta : Pustaka Baru.
- Tiwari, P., Kumar, B, Kaur, M, Kaur G. & Kaur H., 2019, Phytochemical Screening And Extraction: A Review, *International Pharmaceutica Scientia*, 1, 1, 98-106.
- Tjiptono, F. (2018). *Pemasaran Jasa – Prinsip, Penerapan, dan Penelitian*. Yogyakarta: Andi Offset.
- Trisnawati, P, I. (2020). *Manajemen Penyelenggaraan Makanan Pasien Di Rumah Sakit Pusat Angkatan Udara DR. S. Hardjolukito* Yogyakarta. *Jurnal Pendidikan Teknik Boga*
- Widyastuti, Y. *Kesehatan*. Yogyakarta: Fitramaya; 2019:58.
- Willy. (2017). *Pola Asuh Makan*. Jakarta : EGC.
- Yuniarti, V. (2019). *Perilaku Konsumen Teori dan Praktik*. CV Pustaka Setia: Bandung.

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